

METHOD OF USING THE DRUG "ALBENDAZOLE" AS A TOPICAL GERMICIDE FOR THE PREVENTION AND RECURRENCE OF HEPATIC ECHINOCOCCOSIS

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The relevance of research. One of the most common causes of parasitic liver invasions found in surgical practice is echinococcosis. According to WHO, about three million people worldwide get sick with echinococcosis every year. Uzbekistan is one of the regions endemic to echinococcosis [2, 3]. Climatic, geographical, social and economic conditions have traditionally developed in such a way that there are a number of zoonotic foci with varying degrees of intensity of epizootic processes on the territory of the republic [1, 4, 5].

Materials and methods of research. In order to circumvent the negative aspects associated with the use of Albendazole in oral or injectable form, we have developed a chemotherapy technique based on contact antiparasitic treatment of liver tissue with Albendazole and oral administration of this drug in "small" doses (5 mg / kg / day) and conducted a study of its effectiveness in order to prevent recurrence of echinococcosis liver in patients admitted to the multidisciplinary clinic of the Samarkand State Medical University in the period from 2017 to 2020. The essence of the technique is that due to the tamponing of the wound surface of the liver with Spongostan sponge treated with Albendazole solution, a long-term local effect of the drug on the pathological focus is achieved. In accordance with it, we impregnated a sterile sponge with a size of 7×5×1 cm with 50 ml of 0.9% saline solution with Albendazole dissolved in it at a concentration of 10 µg/mL. Albendazole concentration of 10 µg/mL is effective and safe for the patient, which has been proven by numerous experiments by Erzurumlu et al. The study included patients who had:

- 1) multiple cysts;
- 2) cysts with daughter blisters as contents (Echinococcus Hominis);
- 3) single-chamber cysts (Echinococcus Veterinorum);
- 4) calcified cysts;
- 5) cysts of large and medium size;
- 6) cases of recurrent echinococcosis of the liver.

All the patients included in the study were divided into 2 groups: the main group and the control group. The control group included 45 patients with echinococcosis of the liver who took Albendazole according to the standard regimen: 10-12 mg / kg of weight per day (no more than 800 mg per day), three courses of 28 days with an interval between courses of 14 days. The main group included 42 patients with echinococcosis of the liver, who, along with oral administration of Albendazole in the postoperative period at a dose of 5 mg / kg / day, underwent antiparasitic contact treatment of the walls of the residual cavity with this drug according to our method.

The results of the study. After discharge from the hospital, patients were taken under medical supervision with ultrasound, ELISA control and examination of biochemical parameters of the functional state of the liver (ALT, AST) every 6 months for 1.5-2 years. According to the results of the study, a recurrence of the disease occurred in 5 (11.1%) patients of the control group. There was no recurrence of the disease in patients from the main group. There were also no cases of local and general complications in patients treated according to our method.

Conclusions. Despite the small volume of the study performed, the use of "small" doses of Albendazole in combination with the use of this drug as a topical germicidal agent according to the developed methodology showed the presence of a positive anti-relapse effect from their use.

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